

Task 6.13: Project ambassador recruitment and communication

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About this report

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Consortium members

Acronym	Partner
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EMBL	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY
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BIOBYTE	BIOBYTE SOLUTIONS GMBH
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HPCNOW	HPC NOW CONSULTING SL
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UO	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO
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UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA
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ZBMED	INFORMATION CENTRE FOR LIFE SCIENCE
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Rlcapacity	Rlcapacity
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ALU-FR	ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG
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EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE
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Project Overview

The BioNT consortium is dedicated to providing a comprehensive training programme and fostering a strong community for digital skills relevant to the biotechnology and biomedical sectors. Through a curriculum addressing both beginner and advanced audiences, BioNT supports the development of competencies in biological data handling, processing, visualisation, and the use of computational biology tools. Building on extensive experience in digital literacy training and a broad European network, BioNT contributes to the professionalisation of life sciences data management and analysis.

Introduction and Scope of the BioNT Ambassador Programme

The BioNT Ambassador Programme was established to strengthen community engagement, outreach, and the project's long-term impact. The programme actively involved motivated individuals in promoting BioNT's mission, supporting the dissemination of training opportunities, and contributing to the continuous improvement of BioNT training activities.

Beyond dissemination, the programme fostered a two-way exchange between BioNT and external communities. Ambassadors contributed expertise, insights, and perspectives from academia, industry, and training environments, supporting BioNT as both communicators and advocates for digital skills in the life sciences.

A particular focus was placed on sustainability, including the promotion and adoption of online and self-paced learning measures to ensure that BioNT training materials remain accessible, reusable, and adaptable beyond the project consortium.

Role of Ambassadors

Ambassadors served as a bridge between BioNT and external communities, bringing a user- and community-driven perspective to project activities. Their role combined dissemination, feedback, and active participation in the evolution of BioNT training, ensuring that communication, training, and sustainability measures were grounded in real community needs.

Ambassador Programme Development

The Ambassador Programme was structured to provide clarity on roles, expectations, and benefits, while establishing consistent recruitment, onboarding, and communication processes. This structured approach supported transparency, engagement, and long-term involvement of ambassadors in BioNT activities.

Recruitment Activities and Advertisement

Recruitment activities were primarily carried out through BioNT workshops and training events, which represented the main channel for promoting the Ambassador Programme. Workshops provided direct opportunities to engage with participants who were already interested in BioNT's mission and training offerings, facilitating informed, motivated recruitment.

These activities were complemented by the development of dedicated advertisement and communication materials designed to be reusable and adaptable. A LinkedIn post template enabled ambassadors to announce their role and promote BioNT activities within their professional networks, supporting organic dissemination. In parallel, an email template was developed to contact potential ambassadors who had expressed interest, ensuring a consistent onboarding message and transparent communication of next steps.

Recruitment was structured in two main approaches:

- Targeted outreach to individuals who had already applied to become BioNT Ambassadors
- A broader call for additional ambassadors, supported by visually consistent promotional materials aligned with BioNT branding

Visual assets were designed to be clear and readable, with explicit calls to action, such as scheduling links and references to upcoming activities.

Recruitment of ambassadors was closely embedded within BioNT workshops and training activities, which also functioned as key visibility and engagement points for the Ambassador Programme (see Figures 1 and 2).

Represent your community, become a BioNT Ambassador!

Your contribution:

- Share expertise & shape BioNT's direction
- Extend our reach by promoting workshops
- Champion digital skills in biotech & biomed
- Bridge academic and industry communities

What's in it for you:

- Professional development through workshops and mentoring
- Expand your network across biotech & biomed sectors
- Gain visibility via our website and social media
- Help shape training aligned with real-world needs
- Contribute to bridging the digital skills gap

Are you ready to become an ambassador?
Contact us at contact@biont-training.eu

Figure 1: Example of visual material used to promote the BioNT Ambassador Programme during workshops and project activities.

Figure 2: Customisable visual template created for BioNT Ambassadors to personalise and use in the promotion of BioNT workshops and activities within their own communities.

Ambassador Onboarding and One-to-One Engagement

In addition to group-based recruitment activities, BioNT implemented a structured one-to-one onboarding approach with prospective and newly recruited ambassadors. These individual interactions played a key role in aligning expectations, clarifying potential contributions, and strengthening engagement at an early stage. The onboarding process enabled a detailed introduction to the Ambassador Programme, clarification of expected tasks and levels of involvement, identification of individual skills, interests, and community connections, and alignment of ambassador contributions with BioNT priorities.

All onboarding interactions followed established good practices for community engagement and adhered to the Carpentries Code of Conduct.¹

Ambassador Tasks and Areas of Contribution

Through the onboarding process, ambassadors were introduced to a flexible range of potential tasks, allowing them to contribute according to their expertise, interests, and availability:

- Providing structured feedback and sharing expectations based on their community perspectives;
- Promoting BioNT workshops and training opportunities within academic, professional, and student communities;
- Assisting in the dissemination of surveys and evaluation activities;
- Facilitating the transfer of knowledge to local or professional networks;
- Supporting the translation of training materials to increase accessibility across regions and language communities;
- Participating in workshops as helpers, with some expressing interest in trainer or train-the-trainer pathways;
- Contributing to the design and shaping of future workshops, including topic prioritisation informed by community needs;
- Participating in Sustainability, Quality, and Ethics Committees to strengthen the long-term adoption and impact of BioNT outputs.

This flexible task model ensured inclusive participation while reinforcing the community-driven nature of the Ambassador Programme.

¹ The Carpentries Code of Conduct: <https://docs.carpentries.org/policies/coc/>

Benefits for Ambassadors

The Ambassador Programme was designed as a mutually beneficial framework that offers ambassadors clear professional and personal value. Several ambassadors shared their experience:

Through BioNT's ambassador program, I had the opportunity to connect with inspiring people and benefit from their experience and advice.

Haneen Khalil Naim Aljamal

With my experience in BioNT I had the opportunity to learn new programming competencies and to directly give my contribution in shaping the workshops by giving feedback. I am also happy to have contributed in spreading the word about this amazing training opportunity in my network, giving the chance to other people to improve their knowledge about programming.

Valeria Durante

The BioNT Ambassador program has empowered me to elevate my trainer skills through advanced workshops and collaborative community events.

Vanessa González Ribao

Becoming a BioNT ambassador happened exactly at the moment of my transition from a still partly wet-lab-based role to a fully computational one. It was a great way to start connecting with the computational biology community, beginning with the other ambassadors

Roberta Colapietro

Through their involvement in BioNT activities, ambassadors had the opportunity to actively contribute to the design and structure of workshops and future events, while expanding their professional networks by connecting with new stakeholders, experts, and collaborators across Europe.

Ambassadors played an active role in developing the BioNT community and were publicly recognised for their contributions through dedicated visibility on the BioNT website and its social media channels. This visibility supported professional profiling and helped ambassadors showcase their involvement in a European training initiative.

Participation in the programme also created opportunities for career development. Several ambassadors were at early career stages or actively seeking employment, and BioNT supported them by facilitating connections with relevant bioinformatics communities, research networks, and professional initiatives. These connections helped ambassadors broaden their professional exposure and identify potential opportunities within the bioinformatics and life sciences ecosystem.

As part of the Ambassador Programme, ambassadors were given priority access to BioNT workshops, training materials, and selected events. This enabled them to engage early with

training activities, gain direct experience with workshop formats and content, and act as informed multipliers within their communities.

Overall, these benefits supported ambassador motivation, professional development, and sustained long-term engagement with BioNT activities.

Outcomes of One-to-One Engagement

The one-to-one onboarding interactions provided valuable qualitative insights, including the identification of effective dissemination channels such as social media, student organisations, and professional networks. They also led to increased ambassador engagement in sustainability-related activities and supported long-term adoption of BioNT outputs. Additional outcomes included input for future training priorities, such as data visualisation, genomics, single-cell analysis, and train-the-trainer pathways, as well as reinforcement of the ambassador role as both community multipliers and contributors to BioNT's long-term impact.

Ambassador Visibility

As part of the Ambassador Programme, ambassadors are featured on the BioNT website.² This visibility provided recognition for their contribution and supported transparency and community-building around BioNT activities.

Contribution to Sustainability and Communication Objectives

The development and implementation of the Ambassador Programme contributed to:

- Strengthening BioNT's communication and dissemination capacity
- Supporting community-driven sustainability of training materials
- Establishing a structured framework for long-term ambassador engagement
- Increasing visibility and uptake of BioNT training activities beyond the consortium

² BioNT Ambassador Programme: <https://biont-training.eu/ambassador.html>

Conclusion

The Project Ambassador Recruitment and Communication activities successfully established a structured Ambassador Programme under Task 6.13. Through targeted recruitment, structured onboarding, and personalised one-to-one engagement, ambassadors contributed not only as learners but as active stakeholders supporting communication, dissemination, and sustainability of BioNT training outputs.

Their involvement strengthened the relevance, accessibility, and long-term impact of BioNT training materials and supported continued uptake of project outcomes beyond the project's lifetime.

As the BioNT project approaches its final phase, the focus of the Ambassador Programme shifts from expansion to consolidation and sustainability. Key actions in the final months include:

- Continued involvement of ambassadors in the dissemination and visibility of existing BioNT training materials
- Support for the long-term accessibility of training resources, including online and self-paced learning measures
- Documentation and consolidation of the Ambassador Programme processes, experiences, and lessons learned
- Facilitation of ongoing connections between ambassadors and external bioinformatics communities and networks
- Contribution to sustainability planning by capturing ambassador feedback and community perspectives

These actions aim to ensure a smooth transition from active project implementation to long-term availability and adoption of BioNT outputs.